

THERMAL SPIKES ON CFRP LAMINATES: ASSESSMENT OF MICRODAMAGE AND ITS CONSEQUENCES ON FATIGUE LIFE

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ABSTRACT

The fatigue life of (± 45) graphite/epoxy laminates is investigated, with and without previous thermal spiking. A permanent drop of characteristics is found, even in the absence of any observable microscopic damage. The severity of the spike seems to be more important than the number of them; after a certain number of spikes, degradation of material remains stationary.

INTRODUCTION

The outer skins of supersonic aircraft may suffer large thermal excursions, and particularly fast heating, by air friction, up to temperatures of 135°C and even more. These thermal spikes are known to produce important and non reversible changes in the behaviour of composite laminates. A first effect is known as 'anomalous diffusion', or changes in the moisture equilibrium content and in the diffusion coefficient. Mechanical properties can be permanently affected or not, depending on the fiber/resin system, particularly the toughness of the matrix; fiber dominated properties seem to be almost insensitive to thermal spiking. The characteristics of the spikes, such as rate of temperature variation, humidity content of the laminate prior to the spikes, etc influence on its behaviour (1,2,3).

When some deteriorations of the materials properties are found, they are usually explained in terms of microcracking in the matrix and debonding. As far as fatigue initiates by the same phenomena (4), it seems logical that both effects spiking and fatigue can influence each other. The first aim of our investigations was to quantify these relationships. In fact, we had found that thermal spiking reduces considerably the fatigue life of (± 45) laminates, but the mechanism responsible for such degradation is not so evident. Up to the limit of optical microscopy, the appearance of spiked and unspiked laminates was very similar. The damage growth under fatigue follows similar trends, with shorter periods for spiked specimens.

EXPERIMENTAL

A tough graphite/epoxy system was used. Laminates (± 45)_{2s} were produced and cured at conditions specified by supplier (180°C). Specimens dimensions were $20 \times 1.6 \times 220$ mm, with fiberglass tabs. After machining the specimens, the edges were sanded and polished with 5 microns alumina. Static strength was 173 ± 2.8 MPa. Fatigue tests were run in a MTS 810 hydraulic machine, working at 10 Hz, under tensile loading, maximum stress 0.7 UTS, $R=0.1$. Tests were carried out at room temperature, dry conditions.

Prior to thermal spiking, specimens were conditioned to maximum humidity content, which is known to increase the sensibility to thermal shock.

Fast thermal spiking was done by introducing the specimens alternatively into a silicone oil bath (150°C) and cold water (20°C), staging two minutes in each bath. This time is enough to attain a uniform temperature inside the laminate, without altering substantially its humidity content. After a number of thermal spikes (50 and 100), and before the fatigue test, specimens were dried and stored for two weeks to restore uniform humidity distribution.

Before and during fatigue test, edges of the specimens were observed microscopically, looking for initiation and growth of cracks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Life time distribution are given at Table 1

Table 1 Fatigue life under tensile loading, $S_{max}=0.7$ UTS; $R=0.1$; number of cycles.

Unspiked:	81611,	92106,	94520,	95077,	135951,	142400
After 50 spikes:	28915,	38948,	43595,	46538,	62403	, 69220
After 100 spikes:	30990,	36270,	38300,	45322,	61415,	61818

Figure 1 shows the Weibull adjustments for six identical tests in each case. Weibull moduli are similar in all cases (from 3.9 to 4.9), but average values range from 105634 cycles for the unspiked specimens to 47216 and 44890 for the laminates treated previously with 50 and 100 thermal spikes respectively.

Fig.1 Life distribution of specimens

This clearly means that thermal spiking lowers considerably the fatigue life, and that a reduced number of spikes are enough to cause this reduction; an increased number of spikes does not modify the severity of the damage.

Microscopic observations ($\times 1000$) show no significant differences. Before mechanical fatigue, no damage (microcracks or fibre-matrix debonding) is observed in spiked specimens.

At about $1/3$ of life several transversal cracks develop in the outer plies of the laminate; delaminations begin to initiate, and at $2/3$ of life the fracture path can be predicted (fig 2).

Fig.2. Transversal and delaminations cracks of unspiked specimen at 75% of life

Fig.3. Fatigue cracks in spiked specimen at 65% of life

Figure 3 shows a large magnification ($\times 1000$) of a spiked specimen, at the $2/3$ of life. The crack run through the lamina, with some ramifications, but no debonding is observed.

CONCLUSIONS

Thermal spikes can decrease considerably the fatigue life of CFRP laminates, even if no damage is observed by optical microscopy.

The crack patterns under fatigue loading are similar in spiked and unspiked samples, with no signs of debonding.

The severity of damage is not linear with the number of thermal spikes. After a certain number of spikes, the damage does not increase at all.

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